

ORION / Trapezium

JD 2460077

Table of Contents

<i>Preface</i>	2
<i>President's Message by Don Spong (NEW)</i>	3
<i>Vice President's Vision by David Fields</i>	4
<i>ORION May Meeting Information</i>	7
<i>ORION Last Month</i>	10
<i>The Evening Sky Map / May</i>	11
<i>Supernovae Report (NEW)</i>	13
<i>Observatory Way / The Great Comet of 2024? by David Fields (NEW)</i>	15
<i>Astro-imaging by Don Spong</i>	17
<i>Astrophotography at TAO / 19 Apr 2023 by Ted Barnes</i>	18
<i>A Musical Interlude</i>	24
<i>Close</i>	25

Who we are:

ORION was founded in April 1974 by a group of scientists at the United States Department of Energy facilities in Oak Ridge, Tennessee. Our original goal was to perform correlated, instrumented observations of atmospheric and astrophysical phenomena. Since then we have expanded in many directions, including optical and radio astronomy and instrument design and construction.

Future Events:

ORION Monthly Meeting
Monday 15 May 2023
7 pm

See pp.7-9 for details.

TAO Notes:

ORION people are invited to arrive early with binoculars and / or telescopes to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please consider bringing a red flashlight or a headband with a red light, in addition to refreshments. All first time visitors should drive to the site before dark.

Directions:

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

ATTENTION:

Public stargazes at TAO:
Details on p.7.

Trapezium Submissions

may be sent to:
Ted Barnes, Editor,
182 Burley Nelson Ln,
Clinton, TN 37716-6024
or by email to *ted dot barnes2 at yahoo dot com*. MSWord or text files and jpg images are preferred.

President's Message – Don Spong

Welcome to the May Trapezium, our ORION monthly newsletter. Spring is a good time of the year to see a range of galaxies, such as the Leo Triplet, the Virgo cluster, Markarian's chain, the whirlpool galaxy, and a variety of star clusters. I've been imaging some of these, but seems like there's never time to get them all.

The weekend of April 15-16 I had the opportunity to travel to the North East Astronomy Forum (NEAF). This is the largest amateur astronomy meeting in North America and it was very inspiring to experience the comradery with the large community of amateur astronomers who attend this meeting. Attending NEAF had been a goal of mine since around 2018, but due to the pandemic, in-person NEAF was cancelled from 2020 to 2022. NEAF is held in the Rockland Community College in Suffern, New York about 40 miles north of New York city and includes a 90,000 sq. ft. trade show, tutorial talks, talks on citizen science, and more general presentations on space exploration (these included several NASA astronauts, flight directors, and JPL engineers and planetary scientists). Most of the latter talks were recorded and are available through YouTube channels at:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ITV2g5bd9gs&t=8565s> (April 15 talks)

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ikC_Qu-FGVI (April 16 talks)

(you'll want to fast forward through the sections in between the talks)

As you can see below [p.9], there were some large telescopes on display. Also, many of the equipment suppliers had NEAF discounts, and I took advantage of a few of these.

From the Trapezium:

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and amateur astronomy in East Tennessee. We are accordingly closely associated with and support the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) through hosting their public events, sharing our knowledge of the skies using a variety of telescopes, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science with people from all walks of life.

More TAO News: TAOsat tethered balloon launch of 2023 04 23

On Sunday, April 23, the ORION observatory crew and TAOsat team launched and retrieved a helium-filled balloon, supporting our TAOsat instrument package. This was the first of two launches that day. Retrieval wasn't too difficult, since our balloon was tethered. Here's the indoor TAOsat preparation group preparing our package (carrying loop antenna) for flight. Counter-clockwise from right: Dave Rauen, Bob Edwards, Carl Lyster (holding camera), Maegan Hamilton, and me.

Overleaf we see Carl Lyster receiving signals from the UT instrument package with aspiring young scientist Hazel, as she decides to obtain her amateur radio operator's license. Hazel also enjoyed meeting Sunny.

Showing the balloon inflation procedure:

Left: The TAOsat tethered launch, with the balloon just visible at the top of the frame.

Right: After recovery of the TAOsat package we reused the balloon for the UT students (Robbie, Bobby and team), who sent an instrument package to 30 km.

n.b. Some of the outdoor images are from a video record of the event; acknowledgements to Dave Rauhen.

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Our monthly meeting will generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Program presentation and response
- Astrotechnology
- Astrophotography

There will usually be time available at the beginning of the meeting for announcements of general interest.

Please plan to stay until the end of the meeting. We hopefully will all enjoy the astrophotography, as well as discussions of the techniques used in capturing astronomical images.

Information about ORION & TAO

May be found at the following URLs:

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.htm>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

Public Stargazes

The dates and times of these events, which are open to the public, depend on local sky and atmospheric conditions and so cannot be scheduled long in advance. The announcement of these events will be made through the ORIONastronomy email list. One may sign up for email notification at no charge at the email address

ORIONastronomy@groups.io

Title: Experiences at the 2023 North East Astronomy Forum (NEAF)

Speaker: Don Spong (ORION President)

Bio: Don Spong is a fusion plasma physicist who currently works at Oak Ridge National Laboratory on the topic of energetic particle physics in plasmas. He has worked on a variety of other related topics, including whistler interactions in plasmas, Alfvén instabilities, stellarator design, and relativistic electron physics. He has served two appointments as a visiting professor at the National Institute for Fusion Science (NIFS) in Toki, Japan, which operates Japan's largest stellarator fusion experiment.

Dr. Spong received his B.S. degree from the University of Arizona, and M.S.E. and PhD degrees from the University of Michigan. He is a fellow of the American Physical Society Division of Plasma Physics (2016), has been awarded the UT-Battelle ORNL Distinguished Researcher Award (2020), and the Fusion Power Associates Distinguished Career Award (2021).

Abstract: Over the weekend of April 15, 16 I had the opportunity to travel to the North East Astronomy Forum (NEAF). This is the largest amateur astronomy meeting in North America and it was very inspiring to experience the comradery with the large community of amateur astronomers who attend this meeting. Attending NEAF had been a goal of mine since around 2018, but due to the pandemic, in-person NEAF was cancelled from 2020 to 2022. In this talk I will share my experiences and impressions of the 2023 NEAF Meeting, and encourage other amateur astronomers to attend similar gatherings within our community when the opportunity arises.

Meeting Info: Monday 15 May (usual venue) RSCC/Oak Ridge, McNalley Bldg. City Room (A-111) at 7 PM. A Zoom session will be open at the link

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or

<https://bit.ly/42apGxX> Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

ORION Last Month:

Last month's presentation, "Astrophotography: My Journey, with Cats (Part II, finale)," was given on 17 April by Ted Barnes. Dr. Barnes, a Caltech graduate, was the first Joint ORNL-UTK Collaborating Scientist (with the ORNL Physics Div. and UTK Dept. of Physics and Astronomy), and was subsequently a Program Manager at the DOE Office of Nuclear Physics until his retirement and return to the Oak Ridge area late in 2018. This talk, originally prepared in 2020, was deferred until 2023 due to the pandemic.

Dr. Barnes took up Astrophotography in 2015 as an escapist hobby while working as a Program Manager at DOE HQ in Germantown, Maryland. Starting modestly with out of focus images of tree leaves, he proceeded to lunar images, stars, star clusters and asteroids. With a move in late 2016 to a darker sky location, Shafer's Mill near Middletown, Maryland, he was able to capture images of faint galaxies, nebulae, quasars, open and globular star clusters, faint asteroids and TNOs (Trans-Neptunian Objects). This activity has continued with his retirement, including visits to the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) dark sky site. Part II of his talk covered his more recent images from Shafer's Mill and East Tennessee, such as the Rosette Nebula at right which he forgot to include. He is assisted in this work by two black cats, Bucky and Frannie the Astrocat, whose contributions are gratefully acknowledged.

Dr. Barnes has converted his full two-part (95-slide) pptx talk to a pdf of about 15 MB, which is available at <https://bit.ly/44de6TZ> or at the QR code at above right.

Left: Dr. Barnes receiving an award from ORION President Dr. Don Spong.

Galaxy M104 in Virgo.

Rosette Nebula in H-alpha light. 10

The Evening Sky Map

FREE! EACH MONTH FOR YOU TO EXPLORE, LEARN & ENJOY THE NIGHT SKY

Sky Calendar - May 2023

Get Sky Calendar on Twitter
<http://twitter.com/skymaps>

- 1 Mercury at inferior conjunction with the Sun at 23h UT. The innermost planet passes into the morning sky.
- 4 Moon near Spica at 5h UT (evening sky).
- 5 Penumbral Lunar Eclipse from 15:14 to 19:32 UT, mid-eclipse at 17:23 UT. Best seen at mid-eclipse as a slight dimming of the Full Moon. Visible from Africa, Asia and Australia.
- 5 Full Moon at 17:36 UT.

6 Eta Aquarid meteor shower peaks. Most active for 7 days around this date. Associated with Comet Halley. Very fast, bright meteors, up to 40 per hour. Best seen from the tropics and southern hemisphere a few hours before dawn. Moonlight interferes this year.

7 Moon near Antares at 14h UT (morning sky).

9 Venus 1.8° N of M35 star cluster at 17h UT (44° from Sun, evening sky). Mag. -4.2.

11 Moon at perigee (closest to Earth) at 5:07 UT (distance 369,343km; angular size 32.4').

12 Last Quarter Moon at 14:28 UT.

13 Moon near Saturn at 16h UT (morning sky). Mag. 1.0.

17 Moon near Jupiter at 13h UT (morning sky). Mag. -2.1. Occultation visible from North America, Canada and Greenland.

18 Moon near Mercury at 0h UT (morning sky). Mag. 1.7.

19 New Moon at 15:55 UT. Start of lunation 1242.

23 Moon near Venus at 13h UT (41° from Sun, evening sky). Mag. -4.2. Look out for this spectacular pairing!

24 Moon near Mars at 20h UT (evening sky). Mag. 1.5.

25 Moon near Beehive cluster M44 at 7h UT (evening sky).

26 Moon at apogee (farthest from Earth) at 2h UT (distance 404,509km; angular size 29.5').

27 Moon near Regulus at 5h UT (evening sky).

27 First Quarter Moon at 15:23 UT.

29 Mercury at greatest elongation west at 5h UT (25° from Sun, morning sky). Mag. 0.6.

31 Moon near Spica at 14h UT (evening sky).

The Northern Cross is a prominent feature of the constellation Cygnus (The Swan).

In mythology, the dragon (Draco) was slain by Hercules. He is depicted in the sky with his left foot on its head.

NORTHERN HEMISPHERE MAY 2023

SKY MAP SHOWS HOW THE NIGHT SKY LOOKS

EARLY MAY 10 PM
LATE MAY 9 PM
(M1.1 hour time daylight savings)
SKY MAP DRAWN FOR
A LATITUDE OF 40°
NORTH AND IS
SUITABLE FOR
LATITUDES UP
TO 55° NORTH
OR SOUTH
OF THIS

- Symbols**
- Galaxy
 - Double Star
 - Variable Star
 - Diffuse Nebula
 - Planetary Nebula
 - Open Star Cluster
 - Globular Star Cluster
- Star Magnitudes**
- 1
 - 0
 - 0
 - 1
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4

Copyright © 2000-2023 Kym Thalassoudis. All Rights Reserved.
 * TERMS OF USE: FREE FOR NON-COMMERCIAL EDUCATIONAL USE. ASTRONOMY EDUCATION GROUPS
 MAY FREELY DISTRIBUTE PRINTED HANDOUTS. FULL DETAILS AT <http://skymaps.com/terms.html>

WIKI SKYMAPS.COM

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

WIKI SKYMAPS.COM

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

Use the Big Dipper (or Polaris) for finding directions along the horizon. Compass directions are indicated along the horizon.

- STAR ATLAS & PLANISPHERES
- STAR CHARTS & ASTRO POSTERS
- BOOKS FOR SKY WATCHERS

All sales support the production and free distribution of The Evening Sky Map.

SAVE ON RECOMMENDED PRODUCTS • <http://skymaps.com/store>

More sky events and links at <http://skymaps.com/skycalendar/>

All times in Universal Time (UT). (USA Eastern Daylight Time = UT - 4 hours.)

About the Celestial Objects

Listed on this page are several of the brighter, more interesting celestial objects visible in the evening sky this month (refer to the monthly sky map). The objects are grouped into three categories. Those that can be easily seen with the naked eye (that is, without optical aid), those easily seen with binoculars, and those requiring a telescope to be appreciated. **Note, all of the objects (except single stars) will appear more impressive when viewed through a telescope or very large binoculars.** They are grouped in this way to highlight objects that can be seen using the optical equipment that may be available to the star gazer.

Tips for Observing the Night Sky

When observing the night sky, and in particular deep-sky objects such as star clusters, nebulae, and galaxies, it's always best to observe from a dark location. Avoid direct light from street lights and other sources. If possible observe from a dark location away from the light pollution that surrounds many of today's large cities.

You will see more stars after your eyes adapt to the darkness—usually about 10 to 20 minutes after you go outside. Also, if you need to use a torch to view the sky map, cover the light bulb with red cellophane. This will preserve your dark vision. Finally, even though the Moon is one of the most stunning objects to view through a telescope, its light is so bright that it brightens the sky and makes many of the fainter objects very difficult to see. So try to observe the evening sky on moonless nights around either New Moon or Last Quarter.

Astronomical Glossary

- Conjunction** – An alignment of two celestial bodies such that they present the least angular separation as viewed from Earth.
- Constellation** – A defined area of the sky containing a star pattern.
- Diffuse Nebula** – A cloud of gas illuminated by nearby stars.
- Double Star** – Two stars that appear close to each other in the sky; either linked by gravity so that they orbit each other (binary star) or lying at different distances from Earth (optical double). Apparent separation of stars is given in seconds of arc (").
- Ecliptic** – The path of the Sun's center on the celestial sphere as seen from Earth.
- Elongation** – The angular separation of two celestial bodies. For Mercury and Venus the greatest elongation occurs when they are at their most angular distance from the Sun as viewed from Earth.
- Galaxy** – A mass of up to several billion stars held together by gravity.
- Global Star Cluster** – A ball-shaped group of several thousand old stars.
- Light Year (ly)** – The distance a beam of light travels at 300,000 km/sec in one year.
- Magnitude** – The brightness of a celestial object as it appears in the sky.
- Open Star Cluster** – A group of tens or hundreds of relatively young stars.
- Opposition** – When a celestial body is opposite the Sun in the sky.
- Planetary Nebula** – The remnants of a shell of gas blown off by a star.
- Universal Time (UT)** – A time system used by astronomers. Also known as Greenwich Mean Time. USA Eastern Standard Time (for example, New York) is 5 hours behind UT.

Easily Seen with the Naked Eye

- Aur** • The 6th brightest star. Appears yellowish in color. Spectroscopic binary. Dist=42 ly.
- Boo** • Orange, giant K star. Name means "bear watcher". Dist=36.7 ly.
- CMH** • Cepheid name meaning "before the dog" – rises before Sirius (northern latitudes). Dist=11.4 ly.
- δ Cephei** • Cepheid prototype. Mag varies between 3.5 & 4.4 over 5,366 days. Mag 6 companion.
- Denab** • Brightest star in Cygnus. One of the greatest known supergiants. Dist=1,400,200 ly.
- Gem** • Multiple star system with 6 components. 3 stars visible in telescope. Dist=52 ly.
- Pollux** • With Castor, the twin sons of Leda in classical mythology. Dist=34 ly.
- Her** • Semi-regular variable. Magnitude varies between 3.1 & 3.9 over 90 days. Mag 5.4 companion.
- Regulus** • Brightest star in Leo. A blue-white star with at least 1 companion. Dist=77 ly.
- Leo** • The 5th brightest star in the sky. A blue-white star. Dist=25.0 ly.
- Yr** • Red, supergiant star. Name means "rival of Mars". Dist=135.9 ly.
- Scor** • The North Pole Star. A telescope reveals an unrelated mag 8 companion star. Dist=433 ly.
- UMi** • Latin name means "ear of wheat" and shown held in Virgo's left hand. Dist=250 ly.
- Vir** •

Easily Seen with Binoculars

- M44** • Praesepe or Beehive Cluster. Visible to the naked eye. Dist=590±20 ly.
- M3** • Easy to find in binoculars. Might be glimpsed with the naked eye.
- ι Cephei** • Herschel's Garnet Star. One of the reddest stars. Mag 3.4 to 5.1 over 730 days.
- Mel 111** • Coma Berenices. 80 mag 5-6 stars in 5 deg. Dist=283 ly. Age=400 million years.
- ζ Cygni** • Long period pulsating red giant. Magnitude varies between 3.3 & 14.2 over 407 days.
- M39** • May be visible to the naked eye under good conditions. Dist=900 ly.
- ν Draconis** • Wide pair of white stars. One of the finest binocular pairs in the sky. Dist=100 ly.
- M13** • Best globular in northern skies. Discovered by Halley in 1714. Dist=23,000 ly.
- M92** • Fainter and smaller than M13. Use a telescope to resolve its stars.
- R Hydrae** • Long period variable. Mag varies between 3.0 & 11.0 over 390 days. Brilliant red.
- ζ Lyrae** • Famous Double Double. Binoculars show a double star. High power reveals each a double.
- R Lyrae** • Semi-regular variable. Magnitude varies between 3.9 & 5.0 over 46.0 days.
- M12** • Close to the brighter M10. Dist=18,000 ly.
- M10** • 3 degrees from the fainter M12. Both may be glimpsed in binoculars. Dist=14,000 ly.
- IC 4665** • Large, scattered open cluster. Visible with binoculars.
- 6633** • Scattered open cluster. Visible with binoculars.
- M4** • A close globular. May just be visible without optical aid. Dist=7,000 ly.
- M5** • Fine globular star cluster. Telescope will reveal individual stars. Dist=25,000 ly.
- Mizar & Alcor** • Good eyesight or binoculars reveals 2 stars. Not a binary. Mizar has a mag 4 companion.
- Cr 399** • Coathanger asterism or "Brocchi's Cluster". Not a true star cluster. Dist=218 to 1,140 ly.

Telescopic Objects

- Boo** • Red giant star (mag 2.5) with a blue-green mag 4.9 companion. Sep=2.8". Difficult to split.
- Cnc** • Contains 500+ stars mag 10 & fainter. One of the oldest clusters. Dist=2,350 ly.
- CVn** • Compact nearby face-on spiral galaxy. Dist=15 million ly.
- Cas** • Yellow star mag 3.4 & orange star mag 7.5. Dist=19 ly. Orbit=480 years. Sep=12".
- Cent** • Bisected by a wide obscuring lane. Strong radio source. Dist=34 million ly.
- CVn** • Whirlpool Galaxy. First recognised to have spiral structure. Dist=25 million ly.
- Com** • Black-Eye Galaxy. Discovered by J.E. Bode in 1775 – "a small, nebulous star".
- Cyg** • Beautiful double star. Contrasting colours of orange and blue-green. Sep=34.4".
- Cyg** • Attractive double star. Mags 5.2 & 6.1 orange dwarfs. Dist=11.4 ly. Sep=28.4".
- Hyg** • Ghost of Jupiter. Bright blue disk. Mag 11 central star. Dist=2,600 ly.
- Hyg** • Classic face-on spiral. Discovered in 1752 by Lacaille. In attractive star field.
- Leo** • Superb pair of golden-yellow giant stars. Mags 2.2 & 3.5. Orbit=600 years. Sep=4.4".
- Lyr** • Eclipsing binary. Mag varies between 3.3 & 4.3 over 12,940 days. Fainter mag 7.2 blue star.
- UMa** • Beautiful spiral galaxy visible with binoculars. Easy to see in a telescope.
- UMa** • Close to M81 but much fainter and smaller.
- Vir** • Superb galaxy with supermassive black hole at its core. Dist=53.5 million ly.
- Vir** • Sombrero Galaxy. Almost edge-on spiral galaxy. Protruding central core.
- Vir** • Superb pair of mag 3.5 yellow-white stars. Orbit=169 years. At their closest in 2005.
- Vul** • Dumbbell Nebula. Large, twin-lobed shape. Most spectacular planetary. Dist=975 ly.
- M27** •

Supernova Report

Extragalactic supernovae (SN or SNe) are in many ways ideal targets for amateur astronomers. They can appear anywhere in the sky at any time, and are of considerable interest to the public. The brighter ones typically reach magnitudes of 13 to 14, so they are accessible visually in a midrange telescope. Once identified, they usually remain visible for a period of weeks to months. The most common types of supernovae are Ia (accretion-ignition) and II (core collapse).

The discovery rate of new SNe is quite large, due in part to automatic discovery facilities. In 2022, 19297 SNe were reported, just over 50/day. The brightest SN thus far in 2023 has been 2023bee, a type Ia in NGC 2708 which reached magnitude 13.2.

Regular updates of new supernovae may be found on several sites, for example <https://www.physics.purdue.edu/brightsupernovae/> which provided most of the information summarized here.

Since so much detailed data is presented in these dedicated SN sites, which are primarily intended for specialist SN researchers, a summary table of the brightest SNe currently accessible may be of interest. This is presented on the following page, which lists the 16 brightest SNe with an identified host galaxy and their status as of 4 May 2023, with a Northern Hemisphere possible visibility constraint of $\text{Dec} > -35$ deg.

This page will be updated in successive issues, and any new, especially notable information regarding SNe will be presented here as well.

Supernova Report (cont.)

SN	mag		type	host	RA	Dec	Con
2023gfo	14.7		II	NGC 4995	13 09 39.7	-07 50 12	Vir
ASASSN-23cb	14.8		Ia	anon.	06 11 58.5	+58 48 58	Cam
2023axu	15.3		II	NGC 2283	06 45 55.3	-18 13 53	CMa
2023bee	15.4		Ia	NGC 2708	08 56 11.6	-03 19 32	Hya
ASASSN-23ch	16.0		Ia	UGC 11555	20 25 10.7	+05 15 24	Del
ASASSN-23dn	16.0		unk	UGC 12308	23 01 15.7	+14 20 40	Peg
ASASSN-23bo	16.2	*	unk	ESO 549-G29	03 51 20.8	-18 18 37	Eri
2023foa	16.2		Ia	UGC 10678	17 03 59.3	+24 11 11	Her
2023epo	16.2		Ia	KUG 0951+343	09 54 11.6	+34 08 30	LMi
2023eds	16.3	*	II	UGC 11649	20 55 29.2	-01 13 44	Aqu
2023dea	16.3	*	Ia	UGC 2822	03 42 04.7	+41 08 14	Per
2023aub	16.3		II	IC 4219	13 18 31.1	-31 37 50	Cen
2023exm	16.3		Ia	LEDA 170121	11 13 35.9	-14 47 37	Cra
2023eoc	16.4		Ia	anon.	16 11 30.4	+52 27 40	Dra

Table: The current 16 brightest SNe with an identified host galaxy, with a cut on Dec > -35 deg for possible visibility in the Northern Hemisphere. An asterisk * denotes magnitude data over a month old. Updated 4 May 2023.

Observatory Way 2023 David Fields

The Great Comet of 2024?

The photo on the left shows our new TAO road sign. It's on the left as you turn from Caney Creek Road, just past Joiner Hollow Road.

It's dangerous to make predictions about comets – expected comets may be a disappointment, especially if the prediction is more than a year ahead. But consider C/2023 A3 (Tsuchinshan-ATLAS).

Comet C/2023 A3 (Tsuchinshan-ATLAS) was separately discovered and announced by the ATLAS telescope in S. Africa and Purple Mountain Observatory in early 2023, then lost from view. But observations match early observations recorded in the Minor Planet Center. It's a long-period comet with period of about 26000y. That's the period of the Milankovitch cycle, isn't it?

Anyway, if size estimations bear out, this is a large comet that has been out in the Kuiper belt for many years, and the comet tail should be large. Calculations suggest that the magnitude may be 0.3 at peak brightness about October 5, 2024. Mark your calendar.

What is Purple Mountain, and why haven't we heard of it? Purple Mountain Observatory is credited with the discovery of 149 minor planets, over 600 NEO objects, and many comets. It was founded in 1934, and the reason that we don't hear so much about it is that it is located in China. The photo below shows their 60-cm Zeiss reflector telescope.

One discovery of Purple Mountain is the Hildas asteroids, which, like the Trojan asteroids, are associated with Jupiter. Wikipedia says this: “By the late 1980s, increasing light pollution in Nanjing meant Purple Mountain was no longer viable as a working observatory. It has since shifted its focus to public education, with much of the actual scientific work being carried out in its five branch observatories located at Qinghai (in Delingha), Ganyu, Xuyi, Honghe (in Jiamusi), and Qingdao.

The Minor Planet Center credits the observatory, simply referred to as **Nanking**, with the discovery of 149 minor planets between 1955 and 1983, while the observatory's **PMO NEO Survey Program** is credited with more than 600 discoveries between 2006 and 2013.”

Links to additional information regarding Comet C/2023 A3 (Tsuchinshan-ATLAS) are included below.

<https://bit.ly/42uykqB>

Wikipedia

<https://bit.ly/3M2OXV0>

JPL Horizons

I've recently imaged two galaxies, M64 (on the right) and M81 (on the left). M64 is also known by several other names such as the Black Eye Galaxy, Evil Eye Galaxy, and Sleeping Beauty Galaxy. It is a type 2 Seyfert galaxy about 17 million light years away in the constellation Coma Berenices. It gets its name from a band of absorbing dust in front of its bright nucleus. M81 is also known as Bode's galaxy, since it was discovered by Johan Bode in 1774. M81 is a grand design spiral galaxy in the constellation Ursa Major, about 12 million light years from us. Its center contains a supermassive black hole (about 70 million solar masses). Its large size (27 arc minutes) and brightness (magnitude 6.94) makes it a popular target for amateur astronomers. In 2022 it was identified as a possible source of fast radio bursts. These images were both done from TAO on the evening of April 24, 2023, using my 8" Celestron Edge HD scope with a 0.7 focal length reducer and ZWO 183 MC camera.

M64, the Black-Eye Galaxy,
at right.

M81, Bode's Galaxy, at left.

A March TAO dark sky site visit was not possible for me, due to bad weather and to problems with equipment transportation. For April I solved the transportation problem by replacing my used 1999 Honda Odyssey van with a used 2014 Honda Odyssey van, and mastered the removal of the second tier of seats and stowing of the third tier the day before observing night. At the April ORION meeting it had been proposed to move the TAO observing night forward from the weekend of 22-23 Apr, when rainy weather was expected, to Wed 19 Apr 2023. On 19 Apr, sunset at TAO was at 8:16 pm Eastern, and astronomical dusk was not until 9:48 pm Eastern. Since I like to begin setup at least an hour before sunset, I confirmed that TAO would be open by 7 pm (Noah and some astronomy students would be there earlier), packed my equipment in the updated astrovan, and left Clinton for my 42 mile drive to TAO about 6 pm. I fortuitously arrived at exactly 7:00 pm, and began working through my setup procedure.

I set my CGX mount tripod up on the SW corner of the concrete area near the large dome, and levelled it to about 0.1 deg accuracy, which required surprisingly large compensating mount leg extensions. (The concrete pad has a significant slope at that location.) I now have those numbers, and the tripod leg contact points, recorded for future visits. Assembly of the basic structure of telescope, mount and work table took about one hour.

At twilight there was a layer of haze visible low in the West, where some cloud was also present, but we were fortunate and this was less evident later in the evening. Once Polaris was clearly visible I used my OTA's laser as a reference, and adjusted the mount platform in Azimuth until I had the direction to Polaris fairly well approximated. (In Feb I had skipped this step, which is unwise, so I had rewritten my TAO Setup Procedure accordingly.) Polaris was further left than I recalled, from the tripod it was to the left of the Eastern edge of the TAO building roof.

I proceeded to set up the CPU and monitor, and the various cables (three power supplies for the CPU, mount and camera cooler, two USB 3.0 CPU connections to the camera and the mount hub, ASUS monitor power, an HDMI cable connecting the CPU and the ASUS monitor, and a third USB 3.0 CPU port connected to a USB multiport, which connects to 1) a memory stick (for image and log storage), 2) the new ZWO guide scope, and 3) a snazzy new backlit illuminated keyboard with a red color option.

My April mistake was not connecting all the cables while there was still sufficient light to see what I was doing clearly. In the fading light I had failed to connect the little camera cooler supply output power plug to its socket on the top of the ZWO ASI294 camera. If you look closely at the images below you will see only two plugs in the top of the camera (atop the telescope), these being the USB 3.0 and 2.0 connectors. The power plug to the camera cooler has not been inserted!

Accordingly the camera was running at ambient temperature all through the evening and night (confirmed by SharpCap log entries), with a resulting great increase in the number of thermally excited pixels. This little slip cost me hours of compensating post processing work, and I will certainly edit my TAO Setup Procedure to include a visual inspection of both ends of the data and power cables in future. Starting setup 1.5 hours before sunset instead of 1.0 would probably also be a wise change of procedure, and will also be added. I will further add a diagram showing which USB 3.0 cable is plugged into which USB 3.0 slot on the CPU. My current choices work, and I have no guarantee that all USB cables and slots are equivalent.

The next steps were to turn on CPWI, reset the location to TAO coordinates, and begin a new Manual Alignment. With the PHD2 guide scope on (which helps in finding initial stars) and SharpCap on, and I began adding alignment stars for this TAO session. (I didn't record these, but I started with Capella, and used a set of about 10.) At this point I had a scare, I recalled that in Feb 2023, after an hour of aligning, the CPU had suddenly shut down due to overheating. (It's a refurbished Dell laptop.) And the fan was now running continuously. Fortunately Noah was able to find some exam books to stack under the outside edges of the CPU, so no surprise shutdowns happened all evening.

OK, enough about mistakes. By 9:55 pm I was well enough aligned to begin capturing images. Recently, in an online May 2020 issue of Astronomy I had seen some suggestions for galaxies to image at this time of year, primarily in Ursa Major, Lynx and Virgo, so I had scribbled down some of these as possibilities. I added the obvious bright M81 in UMa to the list, which at mag 7.0 it should be an easy initial target. Since Noah had been asking me about shorter versus longer frames in live stacks, we decided to compare my usual 4-sec frames with another live stack using much longer 30-sec frames. PHD2 guiding was used throughout. The latter result, using 48 30-sec frames (hence a 24 min total exposure, finishing at 10:39 pm Eastern), 1570 px square, is shown below.

Seyfert spiral galaxy M81 in Ursa Major

As a quick reminder, M81, also known as Bode's Galaxy, is at a distance of 3.6(0.3) Mpc or 11.8(1.1) Mly, about 4-5 times the distance of the Andromeda Galaxy M31. M81 is a Seyfert galaxy (meaning having an active nucleus), which are anomalously strong sources of IR radiation. M81 has a visual magnitude of 6.9, just below naked-eye visibility.

This image required considerable post processing; since the camera was running at ambient temperature the raw image was crowded with primary-colored (R, G, or B), identically shaped squiggles, due to thermally excited pixels. These were "snipped out" of the image, leaving this view of M81, with a certain amount of residual muddy multicolored noise. A serious comparison of live stacked images with different frame durations will have to wait for another test with the camera cooler enabled.

The next galaxy on my list was NGC 4565, in the constellation Coma Berenices, which is famous as perhaps the most attractive edge-on spiral in the sky. This galaxy is somewhat fainter than M81, at mag 9.6. Visibility is helped by being at a very high galactic latitude of 86.4 deg. This galaxy has a red shift of $z = 0.004095$, corresponding to a distance of 19 Mpc or 63 Mly. The dust lane visible along the plane of the galaxy is reminiscent of that seen in NGC 891 in Andromeda.

This image of NGC 4565 is a live stack of 33 frames, and as for M81, each frame is of 30-sec length (total exposure 16.5 mins), at a camera gain of 450. The exposure was completed at 11:05 pm Eastern. Once again considerable effort was required in post processing to remove the primary colored thermally excited pixels. The final cropped result is 1843 x 1258 px, and appears on the following page.

The "cute" little galaxy at bottom right in this image, pointing towards NGC 4565, is referred to as both NGC 4562 and NGC 4565A, and has a magnitude of about 13.4.

I attempted to capture images of two additional objects, these being the "UFO galaxy" NGC 2683 in Lynx and the dwarf planet 20000 Varuna in Cancer. These attempts at two fainter objects suffered more from the thermally excited pixels, and will hopefully be revisited in future. (Varuna was at mag 20.4, so I tried a heroic stack of 184 15-sec frames at a gain of 540, for a total exposure of 46 minutes. Too bad the camera cooler was off.) Fortunately, at a distance of 44.01 AU from Earth, Varuna won't have moved very far when I get back to it.

Edge-on spiral galaxy NGC 4565 in Coma Berenices

Equipment:

My standard equipment is a 190mm Orion Maksutov-Newtonian telescope (which has very nice optics), a CGX mount, a ZWO ASI294MC-P cooled color camera, a ZWO motorized five-position filter wheel, an Orion 50mm guide scope with a ZWO ASI290MM-mini camera and PHD2 guiding software, and a laser pointer attached to the OTA for when I am totally “lost in space.” For alignment and mount control I use CPWI Telescope Control Software v.2.4.2, and SharpCap v.4.0 for image capture, all software (PHD2, CPWI and SharpCap) running on a refurbished Dell Win10 Pro laptop with an external 24” diagonal ASUS monitor. I also use sheets of 1/8” thick rigid dark red plastic for my PC screen and ASUS monitor, to protect night vision. For post processing I use Windows Live Photo Gallery, which suffices for my needs, and to extract image coordinates I use the All-Sky Plate Solver program (ASPS). To access Gaia data and other “serious” astronomical databases I recommend the French CDS interactive sky atlas Aladin (currently v.11). Finally, for planning observing sessions and locating somewhat faint asteroids I find the real-time sky simulation program TheSkyX to be very helpful.

Units (to 4 place accuracy where appropriate):

1 parsec (pc) = 3.262 light years (ly).

distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 10 kpc.

speed of light = 1 ly/yr. : -)

1 ly = 63.24 kAU.

1 AU = 149.6 Mkm.

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m.

H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 1 change in magnitude = 2.512 x fainter.

+ 2.5 change in mag = 10 x fainter.

+ 5 change in mag = 100 x fainter.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = angle around the celestial polar axis, in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = angle above the celestial equator, in degrees, minutes, and seconds ($^{\circ}$ ' "); analogous to latitude.

RA and Dec, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object’s direction in the sky.

A Musical Interlude

D.R. Fudge (above) and Larry Robinson (below) warming up for another evening of astronomy at TAO with musical accompaniment, 8:31 pm Eastern, Wed 19 Apr 2023.

ORION is an amateur science and astronomy group at Oak Ridge, Tennessee that was founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville, and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and amateur astronomy in East Tennessee. We are accordingly closely associated with and support the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) through hosting their public events, sharing our knowledge of the skies using a variety of telescopes, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs at the observatory. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science with people from all walks of life.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20.00, and student discounts are available.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

Vice President and Program Chair:
David Fields

Secretary: Linda Fippin and Noah Frere

Treasurer: Bob Edwards w/ Noah Frere

Trapezium Editor: Ted Barnes

Astrotechnologist: Rob Scott

Videographer: Rob Fowler

Obed Site Outreach and Oak Ridge Star

Parties: Owen Hoffman

We anticipate a great year for Astronomy in 2023! If you would like to propose new programs or activities, please let us know.

